

Research Article

Eco-Friendly CoCa-Plastics

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Abstract: Over 9 billion tons of plastic have been produced globally since the 1950s, yet only 9% has been recycled. The rest accumulates in landfills, oceans, and ecosystems, taking hundreds of years to decompose. The extensive use of conventional plastic has led to severe pollution due to its non-biodegradable nature and slow decomposition. While biodegradable alternatives exist, they often lack the durability or flexibility needed for practical application. This study addresses this gap by developing organic Eco-friendly CoCa-Plastic, that meet both environmental and functional standards, introducing cassava peel as the starch source, coconut husk as the fibre and aloe vera gel as the plasticizer replacing glycerol. The study presents a novel approach to the preparation of starch-based plastics using coconut husk fibre. The presence of the fibre in the plastics exhibits high water-absorbance, lightweight and strong making it suitable for various applications especially in packaging replacing the conventional plastic, offering an eco-friendly innovative solution to solve tomorrow's challenge that contributes to global efforts in reducing plastic waste driving sustainability for future generations and economic growth.

Keywords: Starch-based plastic; Plastic pollution; Sustainable material

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1. INTRODUCTION

The global plastic pollution crisis has intensified, with approximately 8 million metric tons of plastic waste entering the oceans annually, severely impacting ecosystems, wildlife, and human health (Jambeck et al., 2015). Single-use plastics, particularly those used in food packaging, constitute a significant portion of this waste due to their non-biodegradable nature and extensive usage. Conventional plastics, derived from fossil fuels, take hundreds of years to decompose, releasing toxic chemicals into the environment (Hopewell et al., 2009). This environmental challenge has led to growing interest in biodegradable plastics, specifically bioplastics, which are produced from renewable biological sources.

Recent studies have explored the use of agricultural waste, including potato peels, banana peels, and corn husks, as raw materials for bioplastic production, addressing both plastic waste and agricultural waste management simultaneously. Cassava peels, in particular, are a promising resource due to their high starch content, which facilitates biodegradability. Starch-based bioplastics decompose rapidly in natural environments, as starch is a natural polymer (Sharma et al., 2021). Utilizing cassava peel waste aligns with the "waste-to-wealth" concept, which involves converting waste materials into valuable products (Mohanty et al., 2002). By transforming agricultural by-products like cassava peels into bioplastics, this study addresses forward thinking waste management issues, supports sustainable development, and reduces reliance on petroleum-based plastics.

However, challenges remain in the development of bioplastics. Current biodegradable plastics often lack the durability and flexibility required for practical applications such as food packaging, particularly for protecting dry food from moisture and contamination (Song et al., 2009). Additionally,

the production of bioplastics is limited by the availability of raw materials and higher production costs compared to conventional plastics. Existing bioplastic products, such as PLA and polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHA), have limitations, including low mechanical strength, water solubility, and slower degradation rates under natural conditions (European Bioplastics, 2022). For instance, PLA requires industrial composting facilities for complete degradation, reducing its effectiveness in addressing plastic waste in natural environments.

This study aims to address these limitations by developing organic Eco-Friendly CoCa Plastics a biodegradable polyplastic for plant applications using cassava peel waste. The primary objectives are to synthesize a bioplastic film from cassava peel waste, evaluate its physical and chemical properties, and assess its potential as a durable and flexible material for plant applications, including protective coverings and seedling containers.

Through this study, the potential of agricultural waste materials to serve as viable resources for bioplastic production is emphasized, contributing to sustainable waste management, and addressing global plastic pollution. By aligning with the principles of the circular economy, this study aims to turn waste into valuable products, reducing the demand for virgin plastic materials and promoting sustainable practices. Furthermore, the findings will support global initiatives aimed at mitigating the environmental impact of traditional plastics.

2. METHODOLOGY

2.1 Materials

Cassava peel waste is combined with distilled water, aloe vera gel (4.5g–5.5g), and gelatin (200mL), which act as plasticizers and binders, while standardized fiber additives which is coconut husk (0.1g, 0.2g, and 0.3g) are included to enhance material properties.

2.2 Preparation of Sample

To maximize starch content, cassava peel waste is washed, dried, and ground into a fine pulp, then mixed with 10g of cassava starch, 75mL of distilled water, aloe vera gel, and gelatin, and heated to create a gelatinized solution. This solution is poured into molds of specific dimensions (either 2cm×2cm or 5cm×5cm, depending on the test) and cured at 70°C for 24 hours, with fiber coconut husk (0.1g, 0.2g, 0.3g) added to separate samples to evaluate their impact on bioplastic properties, ensuring consistency across all preparations.

2.3 Fabrication of Eco-Friendly CoCa Plastics

i) Preparation of Cassava Peel Waste

The fabrication process begins with the preparation of cassava peel waste. The peels are thoroughly washed to remove impurities, dried to reduce moisture content, and then ground into a fine pulp. This process maximizes the starch content, which is crucial for forming the primary structure of the bioplastic. Ensuring uniform particle size in the pulp helps maintain consistency in the final bioplastic properties.

ii) Mixing and Gelatinization

The next step involves creating a gelatinized mixture that forms the foundation of the bioplastic. This mixture comprises 10g of cassava starch, 75mL of distilled water, aloe vera gel, and

200mL of gelatin. The components are carefully measured and mixed before being heated to form a viscous gelatinized solution. This heating process facilitates the uniform integration of ingredients and ensures the mixture has the required consistency for molding.

iii) Molding

After achieving the desired gelatinized solution, the mixture is poured into molds designed to meet specific testing requirements. Two types of molds are used: 2cm×2cm molds for biodegradability and water absorption tests, and 5cm×5cm molds for strength tests. The precise dimensions ensure that samples are standardized and compatible with the testing protocols, enabling accurate comparative analysis.

iv) Curing

The molds containing the gelatinized mixture are dried at a controlled temperature of 70°C for 24 hours. This curing process is critical for forming solid bioplastic sheets with consistent strength and durability. By maintaining uniform drying conditions, the fabrication process minimizes variability among samples, ensuring reliable test results.

v) Fiber Modification

To evaluate the impact of fiber additives, the samples are divided into two categories. Standard samples are produced without any fiber, while modified samples are prepared with fiber additives at varying concentrations of 0.1g, 0.2g, and 0.3g. This step allows the study to investigate how different fiber contents influence the physical and mechanical properties of the bioplastic

2.4 Physical Properties Measurement

i) Strength

The force applied to the material per unit area is called stress

$$\sigma = \frac{F}{A}$$

where σ = Stress, Pa
 F = Force, N
 A = Surface area, m²

(Callister, 2006)

The mechanical strength and durability of the bioplastics are tested using larger samples, measuring 5cm×5cm. Each fiber content variation (0.1g, 0.2g, and 0.3g) is tested in triplicate to ensure the reliability and statistical validity of the results. In this test, weights of 20g, 50g, 100g, 120g, 150g, 170g and 200g are dropped from a uniform height onto the samples. The number of breaks or deformations observed is recorded and analyzed to evaluate the tensile strength of the material. This test simulates mechanical stress scenarios, providing a realistic assessment of the material's capacity to withstand external forces. By systematically varying the fiber content, the experiment identifies the optimal formulation for achieving enhanced durability and mechanical performance. Strength testing plays a pivotal role in validating the structural integrity of cassava peel-based bioplastics, especially for applications requiring robust materials.

ii) Water Absorption

$$\frac{\text{Final weight} - \text{Initial weight}}{\text{Initial weight}} \times 100$$

(Water Absorption ASTM D570, n.d.)

To assess water resistance, the same 2cm×2cm samples are immersed in water for a duration of 2–3 days. During this time, the samples are exposed to a uniform testing environment to eliminate variations in the experimental conditions. After the immersion period, the samples are retrieved, and their weight and dimensions are measured. Any changes in these parameters are recorded as indicators of water absorption. This test is critical for determining the suitability of the bioplastic for wet or moisture-prone applications, such as food packaging. Samples that absorb significant amounts of water are classified as unsuitable for such uses, emphasizing the need for materials with better water resistance properties. The water absorption test not only evaluates functionality but also aids in refining the material formulation to enhance its performance in specific applications.

iii) Biodegradation

$$\frac{\text{initial weight} - \text{final weight}}{\text{initial weight}} \times 100$$

(Polymers, 2020)

The Eco-Friendly CoCa biodegradability of the bioplastic samples is evaluated using smaller test specimens, measuring 2cm×2cm. Each sample is carefully buried at a uniform depth in soil that is housed within transparent containers, enabling consistent observation, and controlled environmental conditions. The burial process is maintained for 2–3 days, after which the samples are retrieved for analysis. The primary metric for assessing biodegradability is weight loss, which serves as an indicator of the material’s ability to decompose under natural conditions. By maintaining uniform burial depth and duration for all samples, the experimental setup ensures that the results are both accurate and comparable across different sample groups. This test provides crucial insights into the environmental sustainability of cassava peel-based bioplastics and their potential to reduce waste accumulation.

3. FINDINGS

Figure 1. Strength of Samples

Figure 2. Water Absorption of Samples

Figure 3. Degradation of Sample

Figure 4. The CoCa Plastic Sample

4. DISCUSSION

Based on result shown in Figure 1, the strength of the standard sample is 196 N/m² which represents the lowest strength. Nevertheless, as the amount increases to 0.1 g and 0.2 g fibers, the sample becomes stronger, as it can endure the highest stress of 470.4 N/m² and 588 N/m². Meanwhile, the 0.3 g fiber sample is the higher one, resulting in a notably stronger material. This indicates that the increased proportion of coconut husk in this sample improves its strength. The improvement in strength can be attributed to the lignocellulosic composition of coconut husk, which consists primarily

of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. Cellulose, being highly crystalline and mechanically robust, provides rigidity and tensile strength to the bioplastic matrix (Li et al., 2020). Lignin contributes to the structural integrity and hydrophobic properties of the material, enhancing fiber-polymer bonding and stress distribution. Hemicellulose, on the other hand, fills gaps within the matrix, improving cohesion and flexibility (Shankar & Rhim, 2016). Additionally, the hierarchical structure of coconut husk fibers, with micro fibrils forming bundles and further organized into larger fibrillar networks, reinforces the composite material by preventing crack propagation under stress. All samples containing coconut husk fibers demonstrate significantly higher strength than the control sample, suggesting that the increased fiber content proportionally enhances the pressure resistance of the bioplastic. Further investigations into the relationship between the fiber composition, matrix interaction, and structural arrangement of coconut husk fibers could provide valuable insights into optimizing their application in eco-friendly materials. This study underscores the potential of coconut husk as a renewable resource for improving the mechanical properties of bioplastics, paving the way for innovations in sustainable material development.

Next, based on the result obtained for water absorption over a 10-day soaking period as shown in Figure 2, the standard sample, without any fibers, exhibited the lowest water absorbance which is 22.63% due to its simpler matrix, which likely allowed for less water retention compared to fiber reinforced samples. However, as the percentage of fiber increases to 0.1 g and 0.2 g, the sample provided insufficient reinforcement, leading to increased water uptake value. The 0.3 g fiber sample absorbed the highest amount of water value, likely due to excessive fiber content causing uneven distribution and the creation of micro voids, which significantly increased water retention. This result is primarily attributed to the hydrophilic characteristics of the coconut husk (Shah et al., 2013). The high-water absorption in fiber-reinforced samples can be attributed to the composition of coconut husk fibers. These fibers are predominantly made up of cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin. Cellulose and hemicellulose are hydrophilic polymers with a strong affinity for water, allowing the fibers to absorb and retain moisture (Sgriccia et al., 2008). The 0.3 g fiber sample, with the highest fiber content, had the largest surface area and porosity, facilitating maximum water absorption. In contrast, the 0.2 g fiber sample struck a balance, where the hydrophilic nature of the fibers improved water resistance without creating excessive porosity. The 0.1 g fiber sample lacked sufficient fiber content to effectively integrate with the co-starch based plastic matrix, leading to uneven absorption patterns. Additionally, lignin in coconut husk fibers, being less hydrophilic compared to cellulose, may reduce water absorption in moderate quantities. However, in the 0.3 g fiber sample, the structural inconsistencies caused by excessive fiber content likely overshadowed lignin's water-reducing properties. This highlights the importance of fiber content optimization to achieve desired water resistance properties in biodegradable plastics. However, the 0.3 g fiber sample showed slightly higher water absorbance than the 0.2 g sample, further supporting the notion that excess fibers may lead to structural inconsistencies.

The biodegradability test was conducted to evaluate the rate at which the co-starch-based plastic break down under natural soil conditions over a 10-day period. As shown in Figure 3, the 0.3 g fiber sample showed the least weight loss during biodegradability tests, as the higher concentration of lignocellulosic fibers created a more rigid matrix, slowing down microbial breakdown (Shankar & Rhim, 2016). On the other hand, the 0.2 g fiber sample exhibited balanced degradability, with enough fiber content to enhance the material's structure without overly impeding microbial access to degradable components. The 0.1 g fiber sample degraded more rapidly than the 0.2 g sample due to its lower fiber content, which made the matrix less resistant to microbial attack. Finally, the standard sample, without any fibers, showed the highest weight loss, indicating faster degradation because of the absence of lignocellulosic barriers. The lignin in coconut husk fibers contributes to slower degradation as it is a complex aromatic polymer resistant to microbial enzymes (Li et al., 2020). However, cellulose and hemicellulose in moderate amounts enhance water absorption and facilitate microbial colonization, striking a balance in the 0.2 g fiber sample (Shah et al., 2013). This highlights the potential of carefully controlled fiber content to optimize biodegradability for specific applications.

5. CONCLUSION

This study evaluated the performance of Eco-Friendly CoCa Plastics made using cassava peel as the starch source, aloe vera as a replacement for glycerol, and coconut husk as a fiber additive. The primary objectives were to evaluate the material's strength, water absorbance, and biodegradability to determine its potential as a sustainable alternative to conventional plastics.

In terms of strength, the addition of coconut husk fibers essentially improved the of Eco-Friendly CoCa Plastics's mechanical properties. The lignocellulosic composition of coconut husk, comprising cellulose, hemicellulose, and lignin, played a crucial role in reinforcing the matrix. The hierarchical structure of these fibers enhanced the material's rigidity and strength, allowing the 0.3 g fiber sample to withstand the highest pressure of 784 N/m². This finding illustrates the capacity of coconut husk fibers to improve load-bearing capabilities when incorporated into bioplastics.

Water absorbance testing revealed that the standard sample, without any fiber reinforcement, absorbed the least water (26.23%) due to its simpler matrix structure, which resisted water penetration. On the other hand, fiber-reinforced samples displayed increased water absorption, with the 0.3 g fiber sample absorbing the most water (33.08%). This was attributed to the hydrophilic nature of cellulose and hemicellulose within the fibers and the microvoids introduced by higher fiber content, which encouraged water retention. While the increased fiber content improved the material's strength, it moreover created structural inconsistencies that affected its water resistance.

The biodegradability tests highlighted the impact of fiber content on the material's degradation rate. Over a 10-day period, the standard sample exhibited the fastest degradation, with a weight loss of 3.92%, due to the absence of fibers that could hinder microbial breakdown. The 0.1 g and 0.2 g fiber samples showed moderate degradation rates, while the 0.3 g fiber sample degraded the slowest (0.77% weight loss). This slower rate is attributed to the increased rigidity of the matrix and the presence of lignin, which is resistant to microbial enzymes. The study underscores the relationship between fiber content and biodegradability, emphasizing the need for a balance between structural reinforcement and natural breakdown.

These findings illustrate the potential of Eco-Friendly CoCa Plastics based biodegradable plastics as an environmentally friendly alternative to conventional plastics. They also highlight the significance of optimizing fiber content to tailor the material's properties for specific applications while ensuring fast degradation in natural conditions

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